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A Philip III Tetradrachm Die Pair Recycled by Seleukos I

LLOYD W.H. TAYLOR

A newly identified Alexandrine tetradrachm type struck from a recycled pair of Philip III dies, recut to include the anchor insignia and name of Seleukos, is to be added to the corpus of Babylonia Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis). It represents a new series in the mint's output, Series V(a), that is closely allied to, but preceding Series V in the name of Seleukos. It is distinguished from the latter by the presence of the anchor symbol and the archaized depiction of Zeus. It precedes the decision to eliminate the anchor insignia from coinage of Uncertain Mint 6A and thus must be amongst the first, if not the first coin type to bear the name of Seleukos, die linked as it is to the last of the issues in the name Philip III Arrhidaios, the last of the Macedonian pure blood Argead line. Considered in the context of other die links between different series in the corpus of Babylonian Uncertain Mint 6A, this die link has a ritual character, in effect a numismatic statement of the legitimacy of Seleukos as the successor to Philip III Arrhidaios.

INTRODUCTION

This paper details a newly identified type of Alexandrine tetradrachm in the name of Seleukos I struck from a pair of dies originally dating to the time of Philip III Arrhidaios. Known from a single example (Plate 1, 9) the tetradrachm carries an inverted anchor symbol on the reverse left field, accompanied by the legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΣΕΛΕΥΚΟΥ both apparently recut on a die from the lifetime of Philip III Arrhidaios. The original mint controls of this die were incompletely erased, and a poorly engraved almost indecipherable control was recut beneath the throne of Zeus. The obverse die (A22) was used previously to strike a succession of three issues in the name of Philip III Arrhidaios; the last of the Series I issues from Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia.¹ This obverse die link unequivocally associates the newly identified tetradrachm with the output of Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia,² although its exact position in the sequence of emissions (Series I-V)³ from the mint is not immediately apparent. A catalogue of the known coins from the same obverse die is presented below and illustrated on Plate 1.⁴

¹ L. W. H. Taylor, "From Triparadeisos to Ipsos: Seleukos I Nikator's Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia." *AJN Second Series* 27 (2015): 41-97, cat. nos. 67-74. The obverse die linking issues in the names of Philip III and Seleukos I is obverse die A22.

² Originally located at Opis, after c. 304/3 BC Uncertain Mint 6A evolved into a mobile military mint that accompanied Seleukos and his army on the campaign culminating in the Battle of Ipsos in 301 BC; Taylor, "Triparadeisos to Ipsos," 72-75.

³ Taylor, "Triparadeisos to Ipsos," 47-51 for a discussion of the defining characteristics of each series.

⁴ Images of coins in the collections of the British Museum and American Numismatic Society are reproduced from the PELLA online database (numismatics.org/pella) under the Open Database License (opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0). Additional images are reproduced with thanks to the noted numismatic dealers including Classical Numismatic Group Inc., www.cngcoins.com.

CATALOGUE

Obverse: Head of Herakles r. in lion skin headdress, dotted border.
 Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ in ex., ΦΙΛΙΠΠΙΟΥ on r., Zeus enthroned l., seated with parallel legs, holding eagle and sceptre, dotted border.

Taylor Series I, 67; SC Ad39.7; Price P159.

Σ in left field.

1. A22 P1 15.95 BM 1939,0311.2; GC30.159.

Taylor Series I, 68-73; SC Ad39.8; Price P160.

Σ in left field, STAR beneath throne.

2. A22 P2 16.89 Triton XIV (3 Jan. 2011), lot 349; "Seleucus I" Hoard (CH 10.265).
 3. A22 P2 16.64 BM G.2495; GC30.160.
 4. A22 P2 17.06 ANS 1944.100.34928; Newell, *WSM* pl. XLIII, F; Ankara Hoard 1913 (IGCH 1399).
 5. A22 P3 16.91 CNG 61 (26 Mar. 2003), lot 15.
 6. A22 P3 16.90 CNG 73 (13 Sep. 2006), lot 427; "Seleucus I" Hoard (CH 10.265).
 7. A22 P3 17.14 BM 2002,0101.787; Hersh Coll.

Taylor Series I, 74; SC Ad39.9; Price P161.

K in left field, STAR beneath throne.

8. A22 P4 16.50 BM 1880,0603.26; GC30.161.

Obverse: Head of Herakles r. in lion skin headdress, dotted border.
 Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ in ex., ΣΕΛΕΥΚΟΥ on r., Zeus enthroned l., seated with parallel legs, holding eagle and sceptre, anchor, flukes up, in l. field, dotted border.

Taylor Series V(a); SC -; Price -.

Vestiges of Σ beneath Anchor symbol, Γ (?) beneath throne

9. A22 P5 16.41 LWHT Coll.; Savoca Numismatik 23 (17 Jun. 2018), lot 233. P5 has a re-cut legend and mint controls.

DISCUSSION

Obverse die A22 was paired with at least four reverse dies bearing the name of Philip III (Cat. Nos. 1-8; Plate 1, 1-8) before being used to strike the previously undocumented issue in the name of Seleukos I (Cat. No. 9; Plate 1, 9). At the time of striking the latter, A22 was in its most worn state. Lost through die wear is much of the fine detail of the original iconography, while die breaks occur throughout the mane of the lion scalp. The accompanying reverse die P5 possesses a rigid and formal

style of depiction of Zeus that is similar, if not identical to that of the dies that were used to strike the die linked issues in the name of Philip III. This style is distinctively formal with a vertical rigidity that sets it apart from the balance of the reverse dies of Uncertain Mint 6A.⁵ Prior to the re-cutting of the legend and mint controls on this die, the original reverse die appears to have been cut by the same engraver who was responsible for the reverse dies of Cat. Nos. 1-8. The anchor field symbol of the reverse was engraved over an incompletely erased mint control, possibly Σ . Sufficient detail of the latter remains between the shank and the top left fluke of the anchor to suggest that the original reverse die was possibly used to strike coins of a similar type to Cat. Nos. 1-7, although the underlying original reverse die does not correspond to any of the reverse dies identified in the known surviving coinage of Series I. Either side of the anchor shank small die breaks are apparent, but these do not cut the anchor symbol, which appears to have been engraved on the previously broken die surface. Similar fragmentary die breaks occur beneath the throne of Zeus on which the bracing struts between the throne legs have been erased, although the vestiges of the upper strut can be discerned in the presence of a faintly developed horizontal line of dots between the throne legs, coincident with the top of the semicircular outline, or die break, framing the top of a mint control of which letter Γ may be the primary component. However, the reading of the latter is uncertain due to a number of die breaks some of which overprint the mint control. To the right of Zeus, the original $\Phi\Lambda\text{III}\text{I}\text{OY}$ component of the legend has been incompletely erased and $\Sigma\text{E}\text{L}\text{EYK}\text{OY}$ poorly engraved over it. This was barely successful, with letters ill-defined and traces of the original legend confusingly mingled with the recut letters, so that superficially the legend appears blundered. The contrast between the quality of the engraving of the words $\text{B}\text{A}\text{S}\text{I}\text{A}\text{E}\text{O}\Sigma$ and $\Sigma\text{E}\text{L}\text{EYK}\text{OY}$ is notable, despite the greater die wear on the letters of the former. Examination of the letters E and A, common to both words of the legend, indicates that the two words were unlikely to have been engraved by the same engraver, while the variable definition and differential wear on the components of the legend suggest that the original die saw use while bearing the legend $\text{B}\text{A}\text{S}\text{I}\text{A}\text{E}\text{O}\Sigma \text{ }\Phi\Lambda\text{III}\text{I}\text{OY}$ before the latter component of the legend was crudely re-cut to read $\Sigma\text{E}\text{L}\text{EYK}\text{OY}$. This inference is supported by the die wear on the image of enthroned Zeus, which is lacking detail and bears a number of small die breaks over the design. In particular, the back and the legs of the throne, and Zeus's feet exhibit a very high degree of die wear. This contrasts with the lesser wear on the outline of the anchor in the left field. All factors point to the re-use and re-cutting of a Philip III die from the last of the Uncertain Mint 6A Series 1 mintage, one that dated to the end of Philip III's reign, well before Seleukos took the royal title in the closing years of the fourth century BC.

In Babylonia, the last of the pure blood Macedonian Argead line, Philip III Arrhidaios, appears to have been held in higher regard than Alexander IV, his co-king of mixed Baktrian-Macedonian origin. Tangible evidence of the preference for Philip III Arrhidaios in Babylonia is to be found in the very large number of obverse tetradrachm dies used to strike coinage in his name (Figure 1), plus the fact that during the satrapy of Seleukos the Babylonian mints produced almost exclusively coinage in the name of Philip III.⁶ The pairing of a re-cut reverse die to a worn obverse die used previously for the last of the Philip III emissions from Uncertain Mint 6A suggests the deliberate re-use of a die set in a manner that that could be interpreted to represent ritually on coinage the succession of

⁵ Taylor, "Triparadeisos to Ipsos," 50 and pl. 9.

⁶ Taylor, "Triparadeisos to Ipsos," 65-66.

Seleukos I to the throne previously occupied by Philip III Arrhidaios; in effect a numismatic statement of legitimacy, the coherency of which was emphasised by coinage in the name of each struck from a common die set.

Figure 1. Philip III tetradrachms: number of obverse dies.

SIGNIFICANCE

The new tetradrachm type appears to be closely related to the Uncertain Mint 6A Series IV issue that was struck posthumously in the name of Philip III. Series IV was struck from a recut lifetime Philip III reverse die of Uncertain Mint 6A Series I (Plate 1, A).⁷ On this die, a Γ mint control was added over the Series I Σ mint control in the left field. Although bearing the name of Philip III, this re-cut reverse die is obverse die linked to Uncertain Mint 6A coins in the name of Alexander III (Series II) and Seleukos I (Series V),⁸ an unequivocal indication that this was a late posthumous issue in the name of Philip III. The Γ control appears to be common to both this re-cut Series IV die and that of Cat. No. 9. This suggests that the latter is broadly contemporaneous with Series IV

The legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΣΕΛΕΥΚΟΥ accompanied by an anchor symbol on a die bearing the portrayal of Zeus depicted in a rigid, parallel legs style as found on Cat. No. 9 is the only occurrence of this combination of epigraphy and iconography in the corpus of Uncertain Mint 6A. Prior to the identification of this type, the rigid, parallel legs depiction of Zeus at Uncertain Mint 6A was limited to the Series I and II coins in the name of Philip and Alexander respectively, while the anchor symbol was limited to Series II at the end of which the anchor was erased from the last of the reverse dies in the series. The subsequent Alexander (Series III) and Seleukos (Series V) coinage avoided the anchor

⁷ Illustrated coin is Taylor, "Triparadeisos to Ipsos" Series IV, 189.

⁸ Taylor, "Triparadeisos to Ipsos," fig. 1, obverse die A50.

symbol⁹ while Zeus was portrayed with his right leg drawn back behind the left in a crossed legs depiction.

Logically, the anchor symbol, accompanied by a legend naming Seleukos on a recut Philip III reverse die, must have preceded the decision to eliminate the anchor symbol from the coinage in the name of Seleukos that was issued immediately prior to the Battle of Ipsos.¹⁰ This decision was marked by the erasure of the anchor symbol from existing dies followed by the engraving of new dies in the name of Alexander and subsequently Seleukos without the anchor insignia. The erasure of the insignia from reverse dies involved a number of issues and appears to have been associated with Seleukos's decision to adopt the royal title on return from his eastern anabasis in c. 304/3 BC. This event was closely accompanied by the previously recorded example of Philip III reverse die re-use in Series IV which has been interpreted as a component a ritual affirmation of the legitimacy of Seleukos to succeed the Argead royal line. The temporal association of these events suggest that the last of Series II, represented by anchor erased issues in the name of Alexander, plus the die linked Series IV and V issues in the names of Philip and Seleukos respectively, must all fall in a brief time span in the period c. 304/3-303/2 BC and it is into this period the newly recognised coin type from recycled Philip III dies must be dated.¹¹ This compressed, short duration mintage explains a complex of die links between Series II-V,¹² probably reflecting multiple anvils in operation and a degree of frenetic mintage associated with Seleukos's return from the east, simultaneously with preparations for the deployment of the army into Asia Minor for the final confrontation with Antigonos at Ipsos in 301 BC.

This interpretation carries the implication that the coinage represented by Cat. No. 9 is amongst the first, if not the first, to bear the legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΣΕΛΕΥΚΟΥ (Table 1). It is representative of a new series, Series V(a), that is closely allied to, but preceding Series V in the name of Seleukos. It is distinguished from the latter by the presence of the anchor symbol and the archaized depiction of Zeus. It precedes the decision to eliminate the anchor insignia from coinage of Uncertain Mint 6A and thus must be amongst the first, if not the first coin type to bear the name of Seleukos, die linked as it is to the last of the issues in the name Philip III Arrhidaios, the last of the Macedonian pure blood Argead line. As such it most probably dates to c. 304/3 BC, coincident with the return of Seleukos and his army to Opis following his success in affirming control over the eastern satrapies.

⁹ Closely associated with the assumption of kingship, the anchor symbol was dropped from the iconography of the last of Series II, Series III and Series V, only to be re-instated as a dynastic symbol following the victory of Seleukos's victory at Battle of Ipsos (Taylor "Triparadeisos to Ipsos," 49). One Uncertain Mint 6A Series V reverse die was re-engraved four times and the remnants of an erased anchor can be seen beneath the multiply re-cut controls of the left field: Taylor, "Triparadeisos to Ipsos," 52.

¹⁰ Taylor, "Triparadeisos to Ipsos," 49. The removal of the anchor symbol appears to have been closely associated with the assumption of kingship, perhaps motivated by the desire to remove any vestige of perceived subservience to Ptolemy, for whom Seleukos had served previously as navarch. This step preceded the personal mythmaking of Seleukos, which saw the anchor symbol reinstated as a personal insignia on coinage after 300 BC.

¹¹ Taylor, "Triparadeisos to Ipsos," 62-71 for details of the chronological framework and probable dates of each of Series I-V.

¹² Taylor, "Triparadeisos to Ipsos," fig. 1.

RITUAL DIE RE-USE

The re-use of both obverse and reverse dies from the Series I (Philip III) emission of Uncertain Mint 6A for a coin bearing the name of Seleukos is the fifth recorded incidence of die re-use from another series, or mint, in the corpus of Uncertain Mint 6A (Table 1). It is the only example of a recycled die pair originating from the Series I mintage. Episodic die reuse occurred at significant points in the mint's life including the opening of the mint in c. 318/7 BC, the re-opening of the mint in c. 308/7 BC and the first issuance in the name of Seleukos in c. 304/3 BC. This die recycling phenomenon has a ritual character. Together with the recutting of the reverse dies in two instances it suggests that the re-use phenomenon was intentional, rather than the result of happenstance. In the case of the previously recorded re-use of a Phillip III reverse die (Series IV) involving obverse die linked issues successively in the name of Alexander, Philip and Seleukos, the re-use was interpreted to be a component of a ritual numismatic symbolism defining the legitimacy Seleukos I as the successor to the extinct Argead line, within the framework of the army's acclamation of Seleukos as king.¹³ The identification of coinage from Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia in the name of Seleukos struck from a die pair previously used for the last issue of Philip III strengthens the argument for a ritual symbolism in the coinage; in effect a numismatic statement of the legitimacy of Seleukos as the successor to Philip III Arrhidaios.

Mint	Series	Price	SC	Legend	Recycled Die Links		
<i>Arados</i>	-	3332	-	ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ	A1		
<i>Babylonia Mint 6A</i>	I	P165	Ad 39.4	ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΥ			
	I	P163	Ad 39.4	ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΥ	A18		
	I	P160 P161	Ad 39.8 Ad 39.9	ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΥ			
	II	3434	67.1	ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ		A22	P5 recut
	New Type V(a)	-	-	ΣΕΛΕΥΚΟΥ			
	III	817	49	ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ		A50	Px recut
	IV	P167	68	ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΥ			
	V	-	69.4-.7	ΣΕΛΕΥΚΟΥ			

Table 1. Recycled Dies: Babylonia Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis).

¹³ Taylor, "Triparadeisos to Ipsos," 73-74. At the time Uncertain Mint 6A was transitioning from a static facility, probably located at Opis, to a mobile military mint that eventually accompanied Seleukos's army on its deployment into Asia Minor during the campaign that culminated in the Battle of Ipsos in 301 BC.

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Plate 1

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

A